

Fracture Toughness Measurement for Mode I Fibre Tensile Failure in FRP

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SUMMARY

The compact tension specimen was used to measure the fracture toughness of the fibre tensile failure mode, G_{Ic}^0 , in UD plies. An optimal data reduction scheme was identified and used to investigate specimen geometrical and lay-up effects. It was demonstrated that G_{Ic}^0 is not simply a material property, but dependent upon specimen lay-up.

Keywords: Fracture toughness, fibre failure, damage, lay-up, notch

INTRODUCTION

The fracture toughness associated with mode I fibre tensile failure in a fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) laminate plays a key role in determining a composite structure's damage tolerance and response during damage propagation. To characterise toughness in composites, there is a need for reliable experimental procedures to obtain these properties; results need to be reproducible with low scatter.

Few studies have specifically attempted to measure the fracture toughness associated with *in-situ* ply failure modes. Vaidya and Sun [1] developed a fracture criterion based on the 0° plies in a laminate; the authors concluded that the critical stress intensity factor for fibre failure, K_{Ic}^0 , is a material constant and should be independent of lay-up. Initiation values of K_{Ic}^0 were measured using the centre-cracked tension specimen and found to be approximately equal for the range of laminates tested.

The compact tension (CT) specimen has also been used to measure the toughness associated with mode I fibre tensile failure [2]. The critical energy release rates of the fibre tensile failure mode, G_{Ic}^0 , for fracture initiation and propagation were calculated using an FE based method of data reduction. Fractographic analysis of the test specimens indicated that the measured values may be lay-up dependent.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The baseline CT geometry used a $[(90/0)_8/90]_s$ lay-up of T300/920 carbon/epoxy. The investigated data reduction schemes were the area method, ASTM E399, numerically determined J-integral, and compliance calibration methods.

A modified experimental compliance calibration method was chosen as the most suitable technique; consistent results were obtained and the need for an optically

measured crack length eliminated. $G_{Ic}^{0^\circ}$ was measured for CT specimens with scaled size, increased thickness, and increased ply thickness, see figure 1.

Figure 1. (a) [(90/0)₈/90]_s and [(90/0₂)₈/90]_s R-curves, (b) fracture surface of (90/0) specimen, (c) fracture surface of (90/0₂) specimen showing significantly more fibre pull-out.

CONCLUSIONS

Of the investigated data reduction schemes, a modified experimental compliance calibration method was found to be the most suitable as it does not require optical measurement of the crack length during testing.

The *in-situ* toughness, and associated scatter, of the 0° plies was found to be much higher when blocking 0° plies together, as can be seen in figure 1(a). Fractographic analysis of failed specimens using SEM, figures 1(b) and (c), revealed that much more fibre pull-out was present when the thickness of the 0° layer was increased.

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References

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